

Composted Sewage Sludge as Soil Amendment in Colombia: Challenges and Opportunities to Scale Up

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Abstract:

Composted Sewage Sludge is a rich material that can improve the soil's physical and chemical properties when it meets the corresponding national regulations and follows specific soil and crop needs. This review explores composted sewage sludge (SS) as a soil amendment in Colombia, focusing on its challenges and opportunities for scaling up. Sewage sludge, a by-product of wastewater treatment, is rich in organic matter and essential nutrients but requires proper treatment due to potential contaminants. Compositing SS presents an effective method for transforming this waste into a valuable soil amendment, improving soil fertility, water

retention, and organic content. Despite its benefits, SS composting faces hurdles in Colombia, including limited regulatory support and underdeveloped applications. Colombian regulations, such as Decree 1287 of 2014 and CONPES 4004, provide bases for SS usage but lack updates on emerging contaminants or specific goals for SS deployment. This review identifies a gap in documented experiments and industrial applications within Colombia and highlights the need for enhanced regulatory diffusion and updated standards. It also emphasizes the importance of promoting financial incentives for SS composting projects. The review concludes that while composted SS offers significant environmental and economic benefits, including soil restoration and reduced chemical fertilizer use, realizing its full potential requires addressing regulatory, financial, and research challenges.

Keywords: *Sewage sludge, Composting, Organic amendments, Soil.*

Introduction

Waste generation has become a major global issue. Improper waste management causes pollution, endangering human health, living resources, ecological systems, and countries' economic position (Jebaranjitham et al., 2022). Most waste is attributed to common organic residues, such as food and garden waste, which

make up the largest waste category in the world (UNEP, 2024). However, there are other emerging organic residues from human activities, such as sewage sludge (also known as biosolids), which is a by-product of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Some calculations suggest that the global sewage sludge production rate in 2017 was 45 dry million tonnes (Gao, Kamran, Quan, & Williams, 2020). This material

requires adequate treatment since it might contain heavy metals, microplastics, pathogens, and other harmful compounds that need to be removed, but also beneficial components for soil improvement like organic matter, nitrogen, and phosphorus, especially when it is composted (Urta, Alkorta, & Garbisu, 2019).

Although the use of sewage sludge (SS) as a composting feedstock currently lacks regulatory and financial support around the globe (Urta et al., 2019), there is a growing need for sustainable solutions for sludge treatment. This is particularly important as landfills are filling up and the production of sludge is increasing.

It is encouraging to see that sustainable methods for sludge reuse are being developed, for example, as a soil conditioner to reduce carbon emissions and recover nutrients (Otoo, Drechsel, & Hanjra, 2015). In Colombia's case, the government has taken steps over sewage sludge regulation by establishing quality criteria for SS use in land applications, providing some guidelines for SS treatment, and standards for organic fertilizers and soil amendments (Annex No.3 - RAS and NTC 5167:2022).

Employing SS as an organic amendment or fertilizer in agriculture and horticulture could support global nutrition, promote a circular economy, and reduce chemical fertilizer usage (UNESCO, 2023). Agriculture is a common method for utilizing SS when there is a shortage of soil organic matter. For example, in Spain, almost 100% of biosolids are used in agriculture (Mateo-Sagasta, Raschid-Sally, & Thebo, 2015). As for applications in Colombia, there is still a shortage of documented experiments and industrial applications, requiring an important effort to promote SS as fertilizer and soil amendment.

Globally, sewage sludge reuse aligns with the 2030 Agenda, as the United Nations aims to double the amount of recycled and composted municipal waste in urban and peri-urban regions, which is considered a critical step to accelerate progress (UN, 2023). In addition, SS has the potential to address another global issue related to soil degradation, which has been partially caused by the negative effects of chemical-

intensive fertilizers (Massah & Azadegan, 2016). This is particularly important, as soil is a finite resource in decline, mainly due to human activities and land degradation, which is estimated to account for 20% of global land (UNCCD, 2022). In Colombia, for instance, 40% of the Colombian territory presents some degree of soil degradation (MADS, 2016).

There is still a shortage of information regarding sewage sludge use in soil amendment applications in Colombia. Therefore, this review aims to: first give an overview of SS generation, treatment, and benefits to the soil, and later find the existing national regulations and research studies around the topic to analyze the possible challenges and opportunities for SS to scale up as a product for land improvement in Colombia.

Overview of Sewage Sludge

Sewage Sludge Treatments to be Employed as a Soil Conditioner/Fertilizer

Sewage sludge is the solid material that remains after treating wastewater. Sludge characteristics vary depending on its levels of water content, biological oxygen demand, and sometimes pollutants like heavy metals (Barthod, Rumpel, & Dignac, 2018) or pathogens (Yang, Zhang, & Wang, 2015). There are three common treatments to stabilize sewage sludge after it is generated from the WWTP: anaerobic digestion, composting, and thermal processes (Feng, Burke, Chen, & Stewart, 2023). However, only anaerobic digestion and composting can be employed to produce a fertilizer product. In countries such as Brazil, China, Colombia, and India, anaerobic digestion represents 35–40% of municipal WWTP, while composting and aerobic digestion only cover around 5–10% (Cárdenas-Talero, Silva-Leal, Pérez-Vidal, & Torres-Lozada, 2022).

Anaerobic digestion is a waste treatment process that converts organic waste, such as biosolids, animal manures, or food waste, into two primary products: biogas and digestate (sometimes referred to as AD effluent) (Sheets, Yang, Ge, Wang, & Li, 2015). Digestate is typically semi-solid, high in OM and nutrients (Allen et al.,

2007) and can be directly used as a fertilizer (Mickan et al., 2022). However, sometimes digestates could contain phytotoxic intermediate molecules, while composts are not commonly phytotoxic (Van Der Wurff, Fuchs, Raviv, & Termorshuizen, 2016).

Composting is a process undertaken at high temperatures (> 55 °C) by decomposing raw organic materials (Barthod et al., 2018). This process entails maintaining an appropriate carbon-to-nitrogen ratio, maintaining optimal temperature conditions, and supplying sufficient water and air. The final result is smaller in size compared to the original material and does not have undesirable smells (Allen et al., 2007), phytotoxic chemicals, or pathogens (Mahapatra, Ali, & Samal, 2022). Another similar way to decompose organic matter is called vermicomposting, in which earthworms digest the organic wastes and excrete a nutrient-rich output able to benefit the soil and plants (Georgi et al., 2022).

Benefits of Composted SS as a Soil Amendment

Soil amendments have different purposes and can be categorized as organic, pH, and mineral soil amendments (Allen et al., 2007). In the group of organic amendments are found, for example, manures, compost, digestates, and yard/wood waste. Besides, soil amendments typically address two primary problems: (1) contaminant bioavailability/phytoavailability and (2) poor soil health and ecosystem function (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Soil Amendment Outline

Source: Authors

Organic amendments, including composting, can increase overall soil quality. Besides, compost and its byproducts from decomposition can adsorb onto soil minerals, making the soil less accessible for further decomposition and more stable (Islam, Singh, & Dijkstra, 2022; Kleber et al., 2021).

Furthermore, compost addition to the soil enhances its organic matter (OM) content (Aina Najwa Mohd Nor Azman et al., 2023). When adding OM to landscapes or farms, compost derived from organic residues is commonly utilized, and it allows plants to uptake it more efficiently since it delivers nutrients more slowly and in synchronization with plant demand than inorganic fertilizers do (Manirakiza & Seker, 2020; Ullah, Corneo, & Dijkstra, 2020).

Compost can increase the soil's cation exchange capacity (CEC), improving its ability to retain essential nutrients (Logsdon & Malone, 2015), which is crucial, especially for the fertility of soils that typically have low CEC (Sarti et al., 2023). Besides, compost improves the soil's moisture and water-holding capacity (Logsdon & Malone, 2015), and helps buffer the soil against pH shifts (Kranz, McLaughlin, Johnson, Miller, & Heitman, 2020). Additionally, compost supplements can raise the carbon content of soil (Bai et al., 2023), which improves soil structure and may help to mitigate climate change because they emit fewer greenhouse gases into the soil than alternative methods (Dijkstra & Keitel, 2024).

Sewage sludge is normally co-composted with other raw materials, such as bulking agents (e.g., straws, mature composts, food, or green waste) (Zhang et al., 2021) or different additives (Barthod et al., 2018), which allow for balancing the required initial C/N ratio and moisture content for composting (Malinska & Zabochnicka-Swiatek, 2013) as well as improving the overall product quality. For instance, food waste co-composted with sewage sludge moderates OM degradation, as the organic matter in FW degrades faster than in SS (Luo & Pradhan, 2024).

Sewage Sludge in the Colombian Context

Sewage Sludge Generation

Colombia is located in South America. It has an estimated population of 51.6 million people as of 2021 data (DANE, 2023). The country's increasing population, urbanization, and environmental demands have led to the construction of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP), as these systems allow a safe discharge of the treated water under national permissible limits. According to the National Water and Sanitation Monitoring Report, in 2021, Colombia treated 53.21% of its total wastewater generated (MVCT, 2022). Further, this report highlights that the country aims to reach 68% wastewater treatment by 2030, aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the 2030 Agenda. This intended increase will eventually escalate sewage sludge generation as a by-product of wastewater treatment. Some studies report that the total annual production of SS in Colombia is around 0.15 Mt (dry solids in million tons) and 3 kg/year per capita (Feng et al., 2023).

Relevant Regulation on Sewage Sludge and Soil Amendment

Colombian Technical Norm - NTC 5167:2022. Agricultural industry products. Organic products used as fertilizers and soil amendments

This standard establishes guidelines and requirements for organic fertilizer production and soil conditioners in Colombia (ICONTEC, 2022). It aims to ensure that these products meet specified quality criteria, including limits on contaminants. The standard addresses aspects such as the composition of organic fertilizers, their nutrient content, application methods, and environmental considerations. Compliance with NTC 5167:2022 is essential for producers and distributors to guarantee the quality and safety of organic fertilizers and amendments in Colombia. This standard is managed by a national standards organization (the "Colombian Institute of Technical Standards and Certification" – ICONTEC in Spanish). However, access to the

full text and detailed specifications of the standard typically requires purchasing a copy from ICONTEC or an authorized distributor.

CONPES 4004 (2020). Circular economy in the management of drinking water services and wastewater management

This document presents a policy with certain objectives to improve institutional and governance capacities and implement a circular economy model of drinking water and wastewater management. It aims to be applied over a time horizon of 5 years (2020-2025). The policy mentions that sludge, for its volume and characteristics, has potential as a fertilizer and soil improver in agricultural activities and as an alternative to being an input in energy production. However, the document doesn't specifically cover objectives for SS reuse. It also acknowledges that, despite this potential, in Colombia, sludge is normally disposed of in sanitary landfills (CONPES, 2020).

Decree 1287 of 2014. Use of biosolids generated in municipal wastewater treatment plants

The decree outlines regulations and guidelines for the safe and environmentally responsible management of biosolids as valuable resources for agriculture and soil improvement (MinVivienda, 2014). It establishes criteria for the quality of biosolids intended for land application, including limits on chemical and microbiological contaminants (e.g., metals, coliforms, viruses). However, it doesn't mention any concentration limits for other emerging contaminants, such as microplastics, pharmaceuticals (PhCs), or personal care products (PCPs) (Hoang et al., 2022).

The decree also classifies the biosolids according to their chemical and biological characterization, indicating their potential use (e.g., agriculture, landfills, gardening, energy valorization processes). It also emphasizes the importance of public health and environmental protection around the use of biosolids, aiming to promote sustainable practices in wastewater treatment and agricultural production across Colombia. In particular, Article 20 encourages the promotion

of biosolids to advance actions of recovery, improvement, and restoration of degraded soils.

Annex No.3: Technical Regulation of Basic Water and Sanitation (RAS for its abbreviation in Spanish) Title E - Wastewater Treatment (2010)

It outlines the regulatory framework and technical requirements for the treatment of wastewater to ensure environmental protection and public health in Colombia. The regulation covers aspects such as treatment processes, standards for effluent quality, monitoring and

control measures, and requirements for wastewater disposal. Annex 3 covers the following treatments for sewage sludge: mechanical dewatering, aerobic digestion, anaerobic digestion, gravity thickener, sludge thickening by dissolved air flotation, alkaline stabilization, sludge drying beds, composting, and vermicomposting (MinVivienda, 2010). Moreover, it provides a general description of each system and its applicability. The following advantages and disadvantages are highlighted for composting treatments (see Table 1):

Table 1. Composting Treatment Analysis

Treatment	Advantages	Disadvantages
Composting	Composting reduces sludge volume and converts it into stabilized biosolids valuable as fertilizer. Proper management prevents odors and leachate generation. The required facilities are low-cost.	It demands significant manual labor for operation and continuous attention for control. Energy consumption for aeration and handling is important.
Vermicomposting	Using domestic or agro-industrial wastewater can yield high-value biosolids as fertilizers and soil conditioners, complying with existing country regulations. The structures needed are generally simple and require minimal investment.	Vermicomposting beds occupy substantial space, especially when combined with drying beds. For industrial sludge containing pesticides, heavy metals, and other persistent toxins, the process is inefficient, rendering biosolids unsuitable for agriculture or soil recovery. The process is labor-intensive due to limited mechanization.

Source: adapted from (MinVivienda, 2010).

Sewage Sludge Applications as a Soil Amendment

To collect relevant information on the topic, a search of papers was conducted employing the international database “Web of Science”, covering the period from January 2017 to June 2024. The keywords used were: sewage sludge, soil, Colombia, biosolids, and compost in different combinations. Out of 100 results, some were excluded when repeated, not carried out in Colombia, or not directly related. The studies were chosen specifically when they covered sewage sludge applications as a soil amendment or fertilizer in Colombia (see Table 2 - Appendix).

The search shows a limited number of studies, and those that exist are mainly focused on anaerobic digestion of SS rather than composting, indicating a scarcity of SS reuse for

soil amendment in Colombia. Nevertheless, interest in SS recycling has been observed in some cases. For example, a recent survey addressed to the general public (community) living near a WWTP in a Colombian region (Boyacá) demonstrated that 79.1% of respondents consider that biosolids can be used as fertilizer or compost (Venegas, Sanchez-Alfonso, Celis, Vesga, & Mendez, 2021). Similarly, this study showed that representatives of the public and private entities in charge of the WWTP recognize that even though the biosolids management level is between poor (26%) and fair (37%), they are highly (42.9%) and very highly (35.7%) interested in improving the management and quality of biosolids.

On the other hand, an example of a WWTP that already uses SS as a fertilizer can be found in the city of Cali, Colombia. The municipality produces compost, which is available in the

market and can be used on land and for crop cultivation (Emcali, 2014).

Conclusion

Colombia has important challenges to advance on composted SS reuse as a soil amendment. A key factor is found in the regulation's applicability. Even though the country has related norms and standards, they might not be properly diffused to stakeholders, as there is a lack of applications of SS under the proposed treatments in such norms, including composting and vermicomposting. Besides, the existing regulation needs to be updated to include new emerging contaminants, ensuring that biosolids application in the soil is safe enough for the environment.

On the other hand, in line with the country's goals to increase the amount of wastewater treated by 2030, it should be considered to strengthen a monitoring system on sewage sludge generation and promote financial incentives for WWTP companies and academia to develop projects on SS recycling, following national policies as per CONPES 4004. It is important to note that projects could be financially supported by international organizations (Serrano Alexander & Karen, 2020) and other initiatives focused on circular economy investments in Colombia (BID, 2022). Indeed, the 2030 global agenda for sustainable development calls for more efficient use of water and fertilizers as an agroecological and circular alternative to protect the soil (UN, 2023).

Composted SS is an alternative to traditional chemical fertilizers. Therefore, it represents a business opportunity for companies to commercialize a more environmentally friendly product. In addition, compost has been demonstrated to provide many advantages for the soil, like better water retention, organic matter, and nutrients. Because SS is commonly co-composted, other highly generated residues, such as food and green waste, could be jointly used to improve compost.

Finally, compost application from sewage sludge offers a promising strategy not only for

agricultural soils but also to rehabilitate degraded soils in Colombia, including those that might be impacted by deforestation and mining activities. Composted SS combines environmental benefits with sustainable waste management practices, contributing to soil health improvement, soil restoration, and new economic opportunities.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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Appendix

Table 2. Research Papers on SS Applications as a Soil Amendment in Colombia

Paper Title	SS treatment	Type of soil	Type of crop/plant	WWTP source location	Brief conclusion remarks	References
Biosolids as fertilizer in the tomato crop	Sewage sludge was stabilized with two different treatments: dehydration and the addition of CaO	Greenhouse soil (texture not specified)	Tomato crop (<i>Solanumlycoper sicum</i> L.)	WWTP Sotaquirá, Colombia	The dehydrated biosolids had a more significant effect on the size, fresh mass, foliar area, and number of fruits per plant, compared to the alkaline biosolids.	(Castellanos-Rozo, Galvis-López, Hernández, & Merchán-Castellanos, 2022)
The determination of fertiliser quality of the formed struvite from a WWTP	Biosolids (dried digestate sludge) compared to Struvite from the supernatant of dewatered SS	Coarse sand and sandy soil	Grass (<i>Brachiaria brizantha</i> Marandú)	San Fernando WWTP Itagüí, Colombia	Biosolids showed low nutrient recovery efficiency; however, the author proposes further studies to ascertain the potential eco-friendly application of the combined use of biosolids and struvite.	(González, Fernández, Molina, Camargo-Valero, & Peláez, 2021)
Effect of biosolids on the nitrogen and phosphorus contents of soil used for sugarcane cultivation	Dewatered biosolids that were: anaerobically digested, anaerobically digested and thermally dried, and anaerobically digested and lime-stabilized	Vertic endoaquept with a clay-like texture in a cultivated sugarcane field	CC 8592 sugarcane variety	Municipal WWTP Cali, Colombia	Biosolids yield results were similar to those of mineral fertilizers, suggesting their potential use in agriculture.	(Silva-Leal, Pérez-Vidal, & Torres-Lozada, 2021)
Biological inoculation and organic amendments as strategies to improve ebony (<i>Caesalpinia ebano</i>) tree-seedling growth at the nursery	Stabilized Biosolids (the specific treatment is not mentioned)	Urban soil was taken in Medellín, Colombia. Characterized as loamy sand (Bouyoucos)	Ebony (<i>C. ebano</i> ; Fabaceae)	San Fernando WWTP Itagüí, Colombia	Biosolids provided more nutrients than other amendments, but not the best growth results.	(Hernández Gómez, Osorio Vega, & León Peláez, 2018)
Wastewater Biosolids Composting and Their Effect on <i>Lactuca sativa</i> L. Germination	Compost employing biosolids mixed with <i>Pennisetum clandestinum</i> (kikuyo) grass, horse manure, and rice husk	Non applicable	<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.	WWTP “El Salitre” Bogotá, Colombia	Treatment with 50% biosolids showed better chemical characteristics (C/N 19.08, % CO 28.6, pH 6.3) than other treatments with 60 and 40% biosolids.	(Matiz et al., 2013)

Source: Authors.